

Supporting Information

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Run	X₁	X₂	X₃	Y₁
1	1	4	0.2	88.9
2	10	4	0.2	50.9
3	1	9	0.2	89.6
4	10	9	0.2	11.4
5	1	4	0.8	90.3
6	10	4	0.8	91.4
7	1	9	0.8	90.5
8	10	9	0.8	79.1
9	1	6.5	0.5	91.3
10	10	6.5	0.5	73.3
11	5.5	4	0.5	91.4
12	5.5	9	0.5	87.5
13	5.5	6.5	0.2	54.6
14	5.5	6.5	0.8	90.9
15	5.5	6.5	0.5	98.2
16	5.5	6.5	0.5	91.0
17	5.5	6.5	0.5	94.6

X₁: initial P concentration (mg P/L), **X₂**: initial pH, **X₃**: adsorbent dosage (g/L), **Y₁**: P removal efficiency (%).

Table s9 Full set of experiments of the 2^{5-1}_v fractional design for investigating the influence of inorganic species on the P removal efficiency exhibited by the adsorbent.

Run	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅	Y ₁
1	0	0	0	0	161.4	92.9
2	161.4	0	0	0	0	94.2
3	0	161.4	0	0	0	94.1
4	161.4	161.4	0	0	161.4	95.0
5	0	0	161.4	0	0	95.0
6	161.4	0	161.4	0	161.4	94.8
7	0	161.4	161.4	0	161.4	94.8
8	161.4	161.4	161.4	0	0	94.5
9	0	0	0	161.4	0	95.3
10	161.4	0	0	161.4	161.4	95.0
11	0	161.4	0	161.4	161.4	95.2
12	161.4	161.4	0	161.4	0	95.0
13	0	0	161.4	161.4	161.4	94.9
14	161.4	0	161.4	161.4	0	94.8
15	0	161.4	161.4	161.4	0	94.7
16	161.4	161.4	161.4	161.4	161.4	95.5
17	80.7	80.7	80.7	80.7	80.7	95.6
18	80.7	80.7	80.7	80.7	80.7	94.5
19	80.7	80.7	80.7	80.7	80.7	96.1

X₁: Nitrate ($\mu\text{mol NO}_3^- /\text{L}$); X₂: Carbonate ($\mu\text{mol CO}_3^{2-} /\text{L}$); X₃: Sulphate ($\mu\text{mol SO}_4^{2-} /\text{L}$); X₄: Ammonium ($\mu\text{mol NH}_4^+ /\text{L}$); X₅: Fluoride ($\mu\text{mol F}^- /\text{L}$), Y₁: P removal efficiency (%).

Table s10 ANOVA Table obtained in the FCD for investigating the behavior of the adsorbent.

Source	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Square	F	p-value
Regression	7488.11	9	832.01	15.53	0.0008
Residues	374.9	7	53.56		
<i>Lack of fit</i>	349	5	69.8	5.39	0.1639
<i>Pure Error</i>	25.9	2	12.95		
Total	7863.01	16			

Table s11 Parameters of the statistical model adjusted to the experimental data obtained in the FCD.

Coefficient	Value	p-value
Intercept	90.4	0.0001
A	-14.4	0.0004
B	-5.5	0.0499
C	14.7	0.0004
A ²	-4.9	0.3066
B ²	2.2	0.6371
C ²	-14.5	0.0143
AB	-6.6	0.0379
AC	13.2	0.0014
BC	3.3	0.2371
Parameters of the model		
R² = 0.9523	Standard deviation = 7.3	
R²_{adjusted} = 0.8910	Signal/noise ratio = 15.1	

A: Initial P concentration (mg P/L); **B:** Initial pH; **C:** Adsorbent dosage (g/L).

Figure s5 Photographs of the adsorption media in the presence of organic matter after centrifugation (850 G, 10 min). **(A)** simulated sanitary wastewater without adsorbent (blank); **(B)** simulated sanitary wastewater after contact with the adsorbent. **Conditions:** [adsorbent] = 0,5 g/L, 25 °C, pH 6,5, 30 min, [P] = 5,5 mg P/L, [humic acid] = 50 mg/L.

Table s12 Estimated values for the coefficients of the Langmuir and Freundlich models using non-linear regression.

Adsorption media	Model	Parameter	Mean
Pure KH ₂ PO ₄ solution	Langmuir	Q _{max}	29.73
		K _L	0.31
		R ²	0.69
	Freundlich	K _F	10.96
		n	4.23
		R ²	0.92
Simulated sanitary wastewater	Langmuir	Q _{max}	43.7
		K _L	0.07
		R ²	0.96
	Freundlich	K _F	10.3
		n	3.6
		R ²	0.80

Table s13 Estimated values for the coefficients of Freundlich models using non-linear regression from equilibrium isotherms obtained in different temperatures.

Temperature (°C)	K_F		n		R^2
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>CI 95%</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>CI 95%</i>	
10	11.41	8.28 – 14.64	4.84	3.47 – 7.13	0.96
20	11.44	9.23 – 13.70	4.79	3.80 – 6.20	0.98
30	11.16	8.07 – 14.31	5.64	3.85 – 9.07	0.94
40	10.78	8.28 – 13.38	4.61	3.53 – 6.25	0.98
50	10.66	7.38 – 14.09	5.28	3.54 – 8.75	0.94

* Confidence intervals at significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

Table s14 Thermodynamic parameters estimated for P adsorption in pure KH₂PO₄ solutions.

Temperature (°C)	ΔG_{ads} (kJ/mol)	ΔS^0_{ads} (kJ/mol K)	ΔH^0_{ads} (kJ/mol)
		Mean (CI 95%)	Mean (CI 95%)
10	-35.8		
20	-37.0		
30	-39.5	+0.13	+2.34
40	-39.1	(0.06 – 0.21)	(-20.26 – +24.95)
50	-41.5		

* CI 95% = Confidence Interval ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Figure s6 FTIR analysis of the adsorbent recovered from pure KH₂PO₄ solution and simulated sanitary wastewater.

Figure s7 Diffractograms of the adsorbent recovered from pure KH₂PO₄ solution and simulated sanitary wastewater.

Figure s8 Detection of phosphate ions close to the adsorbent surface after contact with the colorimetric reagent.

Figure s5 Elemental mapping obtained by SEM-EDS of the adsorbent recovered from simulated wastewater